

DIALECT AND ACCENT IN ENGLISH

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Abstract: Modern English today is divided into various dialects and accents. Because English is a public language, so many nationalities are learning English. In order to fully learn the language, it is necessary to study its various dialects and accents together. Learning English is essential for every field and opens the door to many opportunities. Such as business, education, medicine and technology. It is very beneficial to exchange ideas with foreign colleagues to learn these areas thoroughly. In order to communicate with them, it is necessary to learn English, which is a common language, in accordance with their dialects and accents. This article introduces the reader to such a field.

Keywords: accents, dialects, pronunciations

Introduction

Perhaps the easiest way to think of the difference between accents and dialects is to first understand that accents are only a part of what makes up a dialect. An accent is simply how one pronounces words—a style of pronunciation. A dialect includes not just pronunciations, but also one's general vocabulary and grammar.

As an example, someone from the United States may say, "Would you like some tea?", while a person from the UK might instead say, "Fancy a cuppa?" They're both speaking English, and they're both expressing the exact same idea. But not only would the pronunciation (the accent) be different, the choice of vocabulary and the grammar behind both sentences is clearly distinct. Within any given language, both dialect and accent will vary—both largely a product of geography/regionalism. Someone in coastal northwestern France sounds quite different than someone from Paris. A person from the Swabian region of Germany (Bavaria and Baden- Württemberg) will often sound wildly different than another from Hamburg in the north.

- Accent refers to pronunciation
- Dialect refers to a whole group of language features, including pronunciation, but also differences in vocabulary, grammar, and how the language gets used (like the rules of what counts as polite)

So if you and I speak different dialects of English, we probably have some differences in what words we use (maybe I say zucchini and you say courgette), some grammatical rules (maybe I say Do you have any tea? instead of Have you any tea?), and how we use those words (some English dialects say Pardon? and I could too... but more natural for me is Excuse me?).

If you and I have different accents in English, we very probably have other differences too, like the ones mentioned above, but if we're specifically mentioning our accents, we mean only the pronunciation differences. Communities that use a particular dialect or accent can range in size; some dialects include millions of people, and others only a hundred (and some probably even fewer!). For example, North American English refers to the dialect of English used in much of the U.S. and Canada by hundreds of millions of people—but within that enormous super-region are lots of smaller dialects of varying sizes, including African American English, Pittsburgh English, and Southern English.

It's not uncommon for people to feel that they don't have an accent, particularly if most people around them speak the same way, and especially if the people in power around them speak similarly to them. Instead, a language can be thought of as a collection of dialects, all more or less understandable to each other. Or, as internet linguist and 2021 Duocon speaker Gretchen McCulloch recently tweeted "A language is just some dialects in a trenchcoat."¹

Accents have the same underlying principles in all languages, but the result can look different depending on the language! In English, the biggest difference between one accent and another is typically in how people pronounce the vowels. Can you think of any English examples? "Potato" has a whole song about its different pronunciations, where the consonants P-T-T are basically the same, but British and American speakers make the vowels differently. (Note that this is a huge generalization about a global language spoken in dozens of countries around the world, and there are definitely lots of consonant differences across the globe, too!)

On the other hand, many dialects of Spanish have pretty consistent vowels, and it's the consonants that can sound really different. In Spain, most dialects of Spanish have a "th" sound

1 Gretchen McCulloch

(like in English "think") wherever you see "z," "ce," and "ci" written, so casa (house) and caza (he or she hunts) sound different. "R" is also pronounced differently depending on the accent, so in the Caribbean the "r" sound will be

more like an "l" or even an "h," depending on the word and what accent the speaker has (Cuban, Puerto Rican, Dominican, etc). And the Argentinian and Uruguayan accents typically have a "sh" sound, making words like calle (street) sound like "cashe"! (Same caveat here: There definitely can be vowel differences across Spanish dialects! This is a generalization for sure.)

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it is worth saying that English language has a lot of different dialects and accents and quite often people, who speak different dialect don't understand each other. I am strongly convinced that in the learning process it is very useful to learn about various types of language. It will help to understand English-speakers all over the world.

While there are many words that get mixed up in the English language, few cause more confusion than dialect vs. accent. As illustrated above, the two terms are closely related but nonetheless different. Additionally, all of the synonyms and related terms have their own distinct meanings. In closing, we hope you enjoyed this exploration of dialect vs. accent! As always, for all things English conversation, grammar, or job-related.

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